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Waste2Watts: Techno-economic evaluation of biogas-fed SOFC power system integrated with CCS and CCU

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Abstract

Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) system is of great potential for high-efficient biogas utilization. Integrated with carbon capture storage (CCS) and utilization (CCU) technologies, a green power system with low carbon emission will be achieved, which however is of high system cost. In this case, it is necessary to carry out techno-economic assessment to evaluate the feasibility of the integrated system and draw the guidelines for further cost reduction. The preferred capacity for a biogas-fed SOFC power system integrated with CCS and CCU ranges from 20 kW to 200 kW. The comparison of different biogas types and stack technologies is performed first for system performance. Regardless of CCS and CCU parts, the breakdown of levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) is performed to assess the contribution of component costs.

Fig. 1 LCOE results at optimal operating point with stack lifetime of 10 years:

(a) breakdown with no CCS or CCU, (b) fraction of CCS and CCU after integration

The results show that cost reduction in biogas price, stack and biogas cleaning section can significantly reduce the system LCOE. This conclusion is further validated with the sensitive analysis of stack lifetime and clean section cost. The integration of CCS and CCU technology that converts CO₂ into Fischer-Tropsch chemicals and fuels will result in at least ten times more LCOE, which is not suitable for small-scale biogas-fed SOFC system.

Introduction

Biogas-fed solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) system is featured by its high efficiency, flexibility in fuel choice and almost zero pollution. Meanwhile, CO₂ emission is still unavoidable in such an efficient system. According to the Paris Agreement, the balance between the sources and sinks of CO₂ should be achieved after 2050 [1]. To realize carbon neutrality in a biogas-fed SOFC system, carbon capture, storage and utilization technology is introduced. One promising carbon capture storage (CCS) technology is the calcium looping system. It uses CaO/CaCO₃ in a carbonation-calcination loop to separate and capture the CO₂ from the exhaust gas [2]. For the carbon capture utilization (CCU) technology, the Fischer-Tropsch (FT) synthesis can convert CO₂ with hydrogen into syngas via electrochemical or thermochemical catalytically driven processes [3]. However, one biogas-fed SOFC system integrated with the CCS subsystem or CCU subsystem still needs to be investigated techno-economically for the validation of feasibility and scaling effect.

In this study, one biogas-fed SOFC power system is proposed whose capacity ranges from 20 kW to 200 kW. The techno-economic analysis is carried out first without the participation of CCS or CCU technology. Levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operating expenditure (OPEX) are used as the main indexes for techno-economic evaluation. The LCOE of the biogas-fed SOFC system is also broken down to locate the component with the biggest impact on the techno-economic performance. Afterwards, the biogas-fed SOFC systems integrated with CCS and CCU are evaluated techno-economically.

1. System configuration

The SOFC stack model is based on the product from our industry partner SolydEra. The operating parameters of the stacks are listed in Table 1. By varying the recirculation ratio (1% to 90%), external reforming temperature (300 to 800 °C) and fuel utilization (65%, 75% and 85%), the operating maps of the system are derived.

Table 1: Operating parameters of SOLIDpower anode-supported cell stack

Stack Temperature [° C]	Maximum utilization of the fuel	Maximum utilization factor of oxygen	Maximum current density [A/cm ²]
[680,800]	85%	30%	0.5

Two plant concepts have been considered: (1) hot recirculation mixed before the reformer (HB, Figure 1), (2) cold recirculation mixed before reformer (CB, Figure 2). Based on the existing operating maps of two schemes in the previous research, five optimal operating points of each scheme are selected to perform the techno-economic analysis. Meanwhile, considering that it is unrealistic to increase the recirculation ratio of a real SOFC system to 80% or even higher, the recirculation ratio of the optimal operating points is below 80%. The whole system is composed of seven parts: stack, burner, heat exchange network, external reformer, compressors, clean section before the system, CCS/CCU subsystem.

Figure 1: The scheme HB with hot recirculation mixed before reformer.

Figure 2: The scheme CB with cold recirculation mixed before reformer.

2. Economic assumption

When doing the cost evaluation of the system, costs of the components refer to various sources in different years, which are updated to the year 2018 using the ratio of CEPCI (Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index) [4] values to account for the effect of inflation. All the global assumptions during the calculation are listed in Table 2. Meanwhile, when calculating the CAPEX of the components, the engineering cost and the contingency cost are neglected. the capacity of the system is scaled to 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 100, 150, and 200 kW, respectively, to investigate the scaling effect on the system cost. The unit of all the cost equations is euro.

Table 2: Global assumptions for the techno-economic evaluation.

Parameters	Value
System lifetime [year]	20
Stack lifetime [year]	10
Annual production volume of stack [m ²]	30000
Year referred	2018
CEPCI (2018) [4]	603.1
Fuel price [USD/MBtu] [5]	9.3
W2W cost target of clean section [€/kWe]	1000
W2W cost target of the biogas-fed SOFC power system [€/kWe]	2500

Concerning stack, stack enclosure, stack power system, burner and heat exchangers, the cost equations are derived by CEA, France in the Deliverable 3.5 of the project ECo (Efficient Co-Electrolyser for Efficient Renewable Energy Storage).

The cost function of external reformer refers to a report published by the U.S. Department of Energy [6], which proposed a fuel cell system with a capacity up to 25 kW.

For compressors, all the compressors applied are regarded as centrifugal compressors. The material for the compressors is set as carbon steel by default, and their efficiency is set at 80%. The cost of a compressor consists of two parts, the compressor module cost and the electric driver cost, which are calculated according to the book written by Gael D. Ulrich [7].

The Clean section is set before the SOFC system inlet, which provides clean biogas to prevent stack degradation. The cost function refers to the literature [8], which is based on the average yearly concentration of H₂S and equivalent D4-siloxane measured respectively at about 20 and 1 ppm in the biogas. Adsorption system based on activated carbon (either impregnated or mixed with metal oxides) is applied for biogas ultra-purification.

The techno-economic evaluation of CCS subsystem refers to the literature that applies a calcium looping (CaL) based carbon capture system, whose CO₂ capture efficiency is 90% [2]. The cost of CO₂ storage refers to the data collected in America [5].

CCU technology utilizes Fischer-Tropsch (FT) synthesis to convert CO₂ into synthetic hydro-carbons with a high-temperature calcium recovery loop process for CO₂ capture [3]. The CCU subsystem mainly consists of eight parts, namely electrolysis section, direct carbon capture system, thermal integration section, reverse-water-gas-shift section, FT synthesis section, syngas compression section, distillation section and afterburn combustor. Five cases have been investigated in the literature and Case 4 is applied for the SOFC power system with a carbon capture efficiency of 67.2%.

3. Results

Figure 3: Without CCS or CCU, CAPEX of the CB scheme and HB scheme for biogas 1 with (a, d) 65% UFF, (b, e) 75% UFF, (c, f) 85% UFF, whose stack will be replaced for only one time in 20 years.

The system CAPEX results of the 30 chosen operating points are reported in Figure 3. Considering that the conditions among each point don't differ greatly, the CAPEX difference between different operating points is rather small. Precisely, the CAPEX of the HB scheme is a little lower than that of the CB scheme. The lowest CAPEX of 188,810 € goes to HB scheme with UFF of 85%, RR of 60% and reforming temperature of 600 ° C, while the highest CAPEX of 196,995 € goes to the CB scheme with UFF of 65%, RR of 50% and reforming temperature of 700 ° C.

Figure 4: Without CCS or CCU, OPEX of the CB scheme and HB scheme for biogas 1 with (a, d) 65% UFF, (b, e) 75% UFF, (c, f) 85% UFF, whose stack will be replaced for only one time in 20 years.

The system OPEX results of the chosen 30 operating points are illustrated in Figure 4. The difference in OPEX is much more obvious comparing with CAPEX. The key parameter leading to the OPEX gap between different operating points is the different amount of methane consumed. According to Figure 4, low UFF generally results in higher OPEX because of more methane consumed. The operating point of CB scheme with UFF of 65%, RR of 50% and reforming temperature of 700 ° C demonstrates the highest OPEX of 369,370 € at 20 kW system size, while operating point of HB scheme with UFF of 85%, RR of 60% and reforming temperature of 600 ° C at the same size shows the lowest OPEX of 320,754 € during 20 years.

Under the dual effects of the CAPEX and OPEX, the results of LCOE at different operating points are shown in Figure 5. Generally, the high UFF will contribute to the lower LCOE. At 20 kW system capacity, the lowest LCOE of 0.101 €/kWh appears in the CB scheme at UFF of 85%, RR of 40% and reforming temperature of 700 ° C. Notably, the LCOE in the HR scheme at the UFF of 65%, RR of 70% and reforming temperature of 500 ° C is rather high at 0.116 €/kWh. The HB scheme operating point at UFF of 65%, RR of 70% and reforming temperature of 500 ° C shows the lowest system efficiency, which leads to a

higher demand for inlet fuel amount to maintain sufficient electricity output and hence a higher LCOE. On the other hand, increasing the system capacity from 20 kW to 200 kW only contributes to an LCOE decrease of 20%. For example, at the cold recirculation scheme with UFF of 85%, RR of 40% and reforming temperature of 700 ° C, the LCOE of 20 kW system is 0.101 €/kWh, while the LCOE of 200 kW system is 0.081 €/kWh. The ten-time bigger system only has 0.02 €/kWh lower LCOE, indicating that the scaling effect of the biogas-fed SOFC power system is not great.

Figure 5: Without CCS or CCU, LCOE of the CB scheme and HB scheme for biogas 1 with (a, d) 65% UFF, (b, e) 75% UFF, (c, f) 85% UFF, whose stack will be replaced for only one time in 20 years.

Combining the results of LCOE, CAPEX and OPEX, although the operating points differ in price, there is no big variation in the cost structure of each point considering the same calculating methods. In this case, the further techno-economic assessment is based on the best operating point (CB scheme at UFF of 85%, RR of 40% and reforming temperature of 700 ° C) and the worst operating point (HB scheme at UFF of 65%, RR of 70% and reforming temperature of 500 ° C).

Figure 6: Without CCS or CCU, LCOE breakdown at two extreme operating points with replacing stack for one time in 20 years.

To figure out the key factors in the LCOE, we break down the LCOE results, as is shown in Figure 6. At different operating points, the structures of the LCOE are almost the same. Biogas cost always takes up the biggest contribution of higher than 45%, while the contribution of other parts is lower than 10%. Meanwhile, biogas cost increase with the system capacity extension, which is the same as the situation of stack-related cost, including stack cost, stack replacement cost, stack enclosure cost and stack power system cost. The contribution of stack-related cost increases from 17.8% at 20 kW system capacity to 22.1% at 200 kW system capacity. In this case, there are mainly two ways to decrease the system cost, (1) upgrading the biogas generation technology for lower cost and (2) decreasing the cost of the whole stack section.

Figure 7: Impact of the integration of CCS and CCU technology: (a) LCOE results of the integrated CCS system, (b) LCOE results of the integrated CCU system.

The LCOE of the system integrated with CCU and CCS technology is demonstrated in Figure 7. It is indicated that CCU technology is much more expensive than CCS technology. Similarly, the low efficiency of HB scheme (HB65%, RR-70%, Tref-500 ° C) results in higher carbon emission, which hence leads to the higher LCOE comparing with CB scheme (CB85%, RR-40%, Tref-700 ° C).

Figure 8: Fraction of CCS and CCU in LCOE.

Figure 8 demonstrates the cost fraction of CCS and CCU in the system LCOE. Even at the system capacity of 200 kW, the contribution of CCS subsystem in LCOE is still as high as 53%. For CCU subsystem, the fraction at the system capacity of 200 kW is even over 96%.

Conclusively, the cost of CCS and CCU technology is still unacceptable at the kW-level SOFC system.

4. Conclusions

According to the operating maps of the biogas-fed SOFC system, 30 optimized operating points are picked out to perform techno-economic assessment according to the capital expenditure (CAPEX), operating expenditure (OPEX) and levelized cost of electricity (LCOE). The results validate (1) two extreme operating points of the biogas-fed SOFC power system, (2) the key components that affect the system cost most, (3) the feasibility of CCS and CCU integration.

Operating point in the CB scheme with UFF of 85%, RR of 40% and reforming temperature of 700 ° C demonstrates the lowest LCOE. By breaking down the LCOE, it can be concluded that LCOE is dominated by the biogas cost and stack-related cost (stack replacement cost, stack enclosure cost and stack power system cost). The biogas-fed SOFC power system integrated with CCU and CCS has the LCOE of higher than 2 €/kWh and 0.3 €/kWh, respectively. Contributions of CCU and CCS subsystem cost in LCOE are higher than 95% and 50% respectively. Meanwhile, the CO₂ avoidance cost is much higher than the existing CO₂ tax, making the carbon capture technologies unfeasible in a kW-level biogas-fed SOFC power system.

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